

Co-UDlabs

**Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research
Labs communities**

D8.2. Report on determined Scalable Measurement Protocols to Assess the Pollutant Retention and Release Potentials of Urban Drainage Structures

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Background: about the Co-UDlabs Project

Co-UDlabs is an EU-funded project aiming to integrate research and innovation activities in the field of Urban Drainage Systems (UDS) to address pressing public health, flood risks and environmental challenges.

Bringing together 17 unique research facilities, Co-UDlabs offers training and free access to a wide range of high-level scientific instruments, smart monitoring technologies and digital water analysis tools for advancing knowledge and innovation in Urban drainage systems.

Co-UDlabs aims to create a urban drainage large-scale facilities network to provide opportunities for monitoring water quality, UDS performance and smart and open data approaches.

The main objective of the project is to provide a transnational multidisciplinary collaborative research infrastructure that will allow stakeholders, academic researchers, and innovators in the urban drainage water sector to come together, share ideas, co-produce project concepts and then benefit from access to top-class research infrastructures to develop, improve and demonstrate those concepts, thereby building a collaborative European Urban Drainage innovation community.

The initiative will facilitate the uptake of innovation in traditional buried pipe systems and newer green-blue infrastructure, with a focus on increasing the understanding of asset deterioration and improving system resilience.

List of acronyms

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
CSO	Combined sewer overflow
DIBt	Deutsche Institut für Bautechnik
DSM-Flux	Device for Stormwater Monitoring fluxes
JRA	Joint Research Activity
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
MD	Millisil Dust
MONTSE	MONitoring Temperatures in SEdiments
NSE	Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency
PE	Polyethylene
PET	Polyethylene Terephthalate
PMMA	Polymethyl Methacrylate
PP	Polypropylene
PVC	Polyvinyl Chloride
SD	Street Dust
SS	Suspended Solids
TD	Tyre Dust
UDS	Urban Drainage Systems

Executive summary

This document is Deliverable 8.2 of the Co-UDlabs project, funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101008626. This deliverable is an output from Task 8.1.2 of Work Package 8 "Improving resilience and sustainability in urban drainage solutions". The IKT is the author of this deliverable.

The aim of this document is to show the results of research from this work package. The deliverable is a report on the main activities and results obtained within Task 8.1.2, which was focused on the retention of pollution in urban areas using different solutions. The activities were undertaken at different locations.

Combined sewer overflow structures (CSOs) are used to discharge excess volumes of polluted water from sewers into natural waters during heavy rainfall. Microplastics (MPs) are among pollutants conveyed through CSOs and released to the natural environment without any treatment. Within the framework of these investigations by INSA (see chapter 2), the retention of microplastics by a novel stilling basin was examined. The results show that the mean settling velocities of the tested MP and suspended solids, are of the same order of magnitude. A retention capacity of approx. 25 % was determined. Thus, the observations from a 2019 study could be confirmed.

Sediment deposits in urban drainage systems (UDS) has a negative impact on their functioning. The resuspension of these sediments may cause substantial pollution of surface waters via CSOs. Sediment deposits also reduce the storage and hydraulic capacity of UDS. There is a lack of measuring methods and knowledge about the deposition behaviour in order to carry out efficient sewer cleaning. At present there are no reliable, and simple-to-execute monitoring methods to obtain information of the location, amount, and composition of sediments in UDS. A promising approach to measuring deposits is offered by heat transfer dynamics, which has been investigated by UDC and DELTARES for the first time for the application in UDS in laboratory and field tests (see chapter 3).

Permeable pavements in urban areas are designed to ensure that rainwater infiltrates into the subsoil and that pollutants from roads are retained (e. g. microplastic, rubber dust, heavy metals adhering to sediments). Building on the test method of the Deutsche Institut für Bautechnik (DIBt) a new test procedure was developed by IKT and UDC, which simulates a lifetime of 40 years (see chapter 4). A series of laboratory tests were conducted with different kinds of test media. In this context, insights were gained into the clogging process of permeable pavements and there was further development of a procedure for testing their performance using "road pollution" test mediums.

1. Introduction

Urban drainage infrastructure should essentially serve to protect the aquatic environment from pollutants. In addition to the sewage treatment plant, the urban drainage structures (e. g. combined overflow structures (CSO), permeable pavements, gully pots) make an important contribution in this context, provided that regular maintenance and cleaning is carried out. In view of the current discussion on pollutants, e.g., concerning microplastics and heavy metals, the performance of these structures in the retention of pollutants takes on even greater significance.

In this task we conducted experimental research to characterize how pollutants move from urban surfaces, into and through drainage systems under realistic hydraulic conditions. The focus of the investigations was on the performance of new type of Combined sewer overflow structures (CSOs) regarding retention of microplastic, a new approach to measuring sediment deposits in urban drainage systems (UDS) and an improved test method for the performance of permeable pavements.

The results of these investigations will allow improved understanding of the movement and thus impact of urban wash off and pollutant transport processes on water quality of wash off from urban drainage structures into receiving waters for improved ecological impact assessment. In addition, the results create a basis for new product and process developments for the retention and measurement of pollutants. Furthermore, a basis is being created for new test methods for a better monitoring of the performance of these systems at laboratory.

2. Measuring the interception of microplastics by stilling stormwater basins

2.1. Summary

Combined sewer overflow structures (CSOs) are hydraulic constructions that spill the excess of polluted volume during heavy rains to receiving environments. Microplastics (MPs) are among pollutants conveyed through CSOs and released to the natural environment without any treatment. CSO are one of the main sources of MPs encountered in riverine environments. The aim of this study was to investigate the interception of MPs through a novel stilling basin, the DSM-flux (Device for Stormwater Monitoring fluxes, see figure 1), designed to monitor CSO discharges and to trap a part of particulate pollutants. PVC and PET were used as MPs models and were mixed separately in clean water to supply the DSM-flux. After the comparison between the tested MPs and SS (suspended solids) settling velocities, the median settling velocity distribution of MPs was assessed. The results show that the median settling velocities of the tested MPs and SS have the same order of magnitude ranged between 5 and 20 m/h. The interception rate is about 25%. This retention capacity is like SS one as demonstrated in the PhD thesis carried out at INSA in 2019. Further investigations are ongoing to test more polymers and to enhance the geometry of the DSM-flux to increase its interception capacity.

Figure 1. Simplified sketch of the DSM-flux prototype at INSA Lyon (Mate Marin et al., 2018)

2.2. Introduction

Since the industrial use of plastics began in the 1950s, production has continued to increase due to its excellent properties such as lightness, ductility and durability (Derraik, 2002). In 2015, 6300 Mt of plastic waste was produced, around 9% was recycled, 12% was incinerated, and 79% accumulated in landfills or in the natural environment (Geyer et al., 2017). In the aquatic environment, the presence of plastics is a real threat to living species. These microscopic plastics (less than 5mm), suspended in the water, cause two major problems. Firstly, organisms ingest microplastics, which then enter the food chain, impacting humans by ingesting marine products. The second, less visible effect of microplastics is that they form a new habitat for bacteria and pollutants that attach themselves to them (Derraik, 2002). Environmental authorities and governments therefore encourage the monitoring of urban wet weather discharges and the collection of reliable data on their impact. However, monitoring and measuring these discharges is a real challenge because hydraulic structures are not adapted and measurements depend on many factors, such as its representativeness and hydraulic conditions. As a result, few barriers exist, particularly for the treatment of combined sewer overflows.

In response to this environmental concern and monitoring challenge, a new measuring device has been designed: the DSM Flux, which stands for Device for Stormwater Monitoring and Controlling Pollutant Fluxes (Mate Marin et al., 2018). This is a pre-calibrated, pre-designed device for measuring flow rates and volumes discharged, as well as concentrations and masses of pollutants. It also captures particulate pollutants by sedimentation. The advantages of this technology are numerous: it operates independently from the geometry of upstream CSOs, its implementation is adapted for complex site, and it provides appropriate hydraulic conditions for accurate and reliable continuous monitoring (Mate Marin et al., 2018).

The DSM Flux has been the subject of previous studies. Its initial design was optimised in 2014 and then its reliability and ability to settle particulate pollutants were evaluated by Mate Marin (2019). All those previous investigations demonstrated the ability of the DSM flux to trap SS. That is why its capability to intercept MPs has been investigated.

The aim of this research work is to evaluate the capacity of the DSM-flux to intercept MPs conveyed in clean water. In other words, the following questions are addressed:

1. Is the settling velocity of MPs like the SS one so that they can be trapped by the DSM-Flux?
2. Is the DSM-Flux capable to effectively intercept MPs in clean water?

2.3. Material and Methods

2.3.1. Selection and characterization of tested MP

Microplastics (MPs) are fragments of polymers. Different sizes and types of MPs can be found in the environment. Any plastic particle between 1 μ m and 5mm is called a microplastic. In order to select appropriate MPs for our experiments, we did a thorough literature review demonstrating that the polymers that are encountered the most in natural environments are PP (polypropylene), PE (polyethylene) and PET (Waldschlager & Schuttrumpf, 2019). This observation was also supported by Geyer et al. (2017) as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Production of plastic wastes according to the type of polymer, data collected in 2015 (Geyer et al., 2017)

Then additional preliminary experiments enabled to select PVC and PET. Settling velocity measurement (using VICAS protocol – Chebbo & Gromaire, 2009), grain size distribution and gravimetry have been carried out to better characterize the selected MPs.

2.3.2. Protocol for MPs interception in the DSM-flux

The DSM-flux is an original flume for water quality and quantity measurement. Its design also enables to trap a fraction of suspended solids (Mate Marin et al., 2018). The aim of the experiment is to evaluate the interception rate of MPs through the DSM-flux device. MPs are first mixed with clean water in a beaker and then injected approximately 1.5 m upstream into the inlet pipe using a peristaltic pump. As the injection tube is kept above the flow, no disturbance is created in the flow entering the DSM Flux. MPs escaped from the DSM-flux are collected using an 80 μ m sieve. It was decided to experiment only with PVC MPs. In order to reduce uncertainty and obtain the most accurate results, several tests were carried out under conditions that were as similar as possible (repeatability tests). The flow rate along all experiments was 5 l/s. 8g of PVC MPs were injected. Figure 3 indicates key steps of the protocol.

1.MPs preparation

2.Injection using peristaltic pump

3.Interception

4.Filtration

Figure 3. Protocol for the measurement of MPs interception rate in DSM-flux prototype (Kisterman & De Lorgeril, 2023)

2.4. Preliminary results and concluding remarks

Results shown in figure 4 indicate that for 20% of the mass of MPs, PVC has a higher settling velocity than PET. It is the opposite for more than 40% of the mass of MPs. Densities of PVC and PET are almost the same. The observed variation may be due to interaction between particles during the VICAS process.

Figure 4. Settling velocity distribution – $F(V_s)$ curve indicates the cumulative percentage F in % of total MPs particle mass with a settling velocity below V_s in mm/s

In addition, the higher the concentration, the higher the settling velocity. A similar result has already been observed by Waldschlager & Schuttrumpf (2019).

Regarding the interception rate, all preliminary results are gathered in Table 1.

Table 1. Interception rate of MPs through the DSM-flux original flume

Experiments	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Injected mass (g)	7,049	6,064	8,061	8,013	8,06	8,011	8,013
Escaped mass (g)	5,237	4,788	6,07	6,322	6,321	6,1g	5,964
Trapped rate (%)	25,71%	21,04%	24,70%	21,10%	21,58%	23,85%	25,57%

In this research project, two questions were addressed: is the settling velocity of MPs similar to that of suspended solids so that they can be trapped in the DSM Flux? Is the DSM-flux capable to effectively intercept MPs in clean water?

The study focused on PVC and PET particles with sizes ranging from 80µm to 500µm and densities of 1.36 and 1.38 respectively. To address the scientific questions, the study was divided into two parts. The first part looked at the settling velocity of MPs using the VICAS protocol. Results showed that the settling velocity of investigated MPs had the same order of magnitude as that of suspended solids. The results of the study also show that the higher the MPs concentration, the faster the particles settle.

The interception rate of MPs through the DSM-flux was also assessed. The results showed that the interception rate is 25% particularly for PVC MPs at a flow rate of 5 L/s. INSA is involved in a national program on MPs sources, transport and fate in urban drainage.

3. Measuring sediment deposits in urban drainage infrastructure from high-resolution temperature signals

The presence of sediments in urban drainage systems (UDS) has a negative impact on their functioning. For instance, the resuspension of these sediments may cause substantial pollution of surface waters via combined sewer overflows (CSO). In addition, the persistent sediment accumulation reduces the storage and hydraulic capacity of UDS resulting in an increased risk of flooding (Ashley et al, 2004).

UDS managers spend substantial amount of means and budget to clean out UDS on a regular basis, but there is still a lack of consensus on inspection work frequency (Ertl et al., 2022). One of the main practical issues at present is that there are currently no reliable, and simple-to-execute monitoring methods to obtain information of the location, amount, and composition of sediments in UDS. Recent attempts to monitor sediment bed deposits consisted mostly of single-period measurements that required a high cost of supervision and maintenance, e.g., Lepot et al. (2017), Oms et al. (2003), and Shahsavari et al. (2017). Therefore, sediment monitoring in UDS remains challenging.

The idea behind this research is to use heat transfer processes in UDS as a proxy for measuring sediment-bed accumulation. Studies in river streambeds proved the application of methodologies based on the analysis of daily temperature patterns to measure accumulation and erosion processes (DeWeese et al., 2017; Sebok et al., 2017). As for urban drainage systems, the application of heat transfer dynamics for measuring sediment accumulation has, to the authors' knowledge, not been explored in the literature so far. Nevertheless, recent studies advanced towards the description of heat transfer processes in UDS infrastructures, such as sewer pipes, especially the fluid-headspace-soil interaction (Abdel-Aal et al., 2021; Figueroa et al., 2021). The current research further extends this analysis by including heat transfer processes regarding the presence of sediment accumulation.

3.1. Fundamentals of heat transfer processes in urban drainage systems.

Understanding the heat transfer processes occurring in UDS is essential to be able to analyze the temperature time series and their relationship to sediment depths. For this purpose, the first step consisted of developing a pilot experimental campaign in a reduced laboratory model with sediments from a local manhole in A Coruña (Spain). The aim of this experimental setup was to measure the differences between temperature time series in the water layer and the sediment bottom depending on the sediment depth.

The experimental setup consisted of four adiabatic boxes of 15×15×15 cm³ (inner dimensions) made of Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) to avoid significant heat transfer at the contours. Sediment thicknesses of 2, 4, 6 and 8 cm were respectively poured at the bottom of each box together with 2 cm layer of water covering them. Two temperature sensors were installed in each box for measuring the water and sediment-bed temperatures. In addition, each box included a coil system to introduce temperature gradients in the water layer by pumping water from a temperature-controlled system. This system consisted of a water bath with heating and cooling devices attached, and four pond pumps (200 L/h) to supply temperature oscillations to each box. Finally, two additional temperature sensors were set for measuring the room and water bath temperatures, respectively. Figure 5 summarizes the experimental setup performed in the Hydraulics Laboratory of the Civil Engineering School at the Universidade da Coruña (A Coruña, Spain).

Figure 5. Photo of the experimental setup. Source: Anta et al. (2022).

Two experimental procedures were carried out:

- Pulse experiments (Figure 6a): these tests consist in short period increases of the water layer temperature within the boxes. The water was warmed up to 2°C in 20 minutes, simulating heat dynamics due to sharp temperature gradients, such as stormwater inflows.
- Cycle experiments (Figure 6b): conversely previous procedure, these tests forced a prolonged heat-cooling cycle in the water layer. Cycles consisted of a 2-hour heating and a subsequent cooling. Water temperature oscillations were set in the range of 2°C, simulating daily temperature oscillations in wastewater or drainage water (Montserrat et al., 2013).

Each experimental procedure was applied to each box. Therefore, 8 tests were performed. The data from this experimental campaign are available in Anta et al. (2022).

Figure 6. Scheme of experimental procedures: pulse (left) and cycle (right). Source: Anta et al. (2022).

The results showed a correlation between the sediment depth and the attenuation and time-lag of the sediment-bed temperatures compared to the water temperatures. The greater the sediment depth, the greater the attenuation and time-lag of the temperature signal. A numerical model was developed to simulate the heat transfer process through the sediment layer by solving the diffusion heat transfer equation. This model included an upper boundary condition, defined by the temperature of the water layer, and a lower boundary condition, defined by a convective heat transfer condition. The simulated temperature series at the bottom of the sediment layer were compared with experimental measurements to evaluate the performance of the numerical model. A strong correlation between the experimental and numerical temperature series has been obtained in most cases, with Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE) coefficients greater than 0.90, except for the pulse test with the smallest sediment depth ($H_{sed} = 2$ cm). Figure 7 shows the temperature time series in the water layer and sediment bottom of the experimental campaign, as well as the comparison with the simulated temperature series at the bottom of the sediment layer.

Figure 7. Pulse (left column) and cycle (right column) lab-scale tests: experimental and numerical comparison. Experimental water (blue line) and sediment-bed (orange line) temperatures, and best-fit simulated sediment-bed temperatures (dashed brown line). Source: Regueiro-Picallo et al. (2023a).

This experimental campaign proved the possibility of correlating the time lag and the attenuation between the water and sediment-bed temperature series with the sediment depth. In addition, a numerical model could be developed to simulate the temperature series at the bottom of the sediment layer by introducing the water temperature as an upper boundary condition and a convective heat transfer condition at the lower boundary. Knowing the thermal properties of the sediments and the convective heat transfer coefficient at the bottom were also required to run the model.

Multiple scenarios with different sediment depths, thermal properties and convective heat transfer coefficients can be simulated by using this numerical model. Consequently, surrogate models can be developed based on the analysis of the attenuations of the temperature series to estimate the sediment depth (Regueiro-Picallo et al., 2023a). For example, wastewater temperature series in combined sewer pipes follow a sinusoidal daily pattern under dry weather conditions. Thus, the fundamental frequency (or first harmonic) can be analyzed and compared with the corresponding attenuation and phase shift of the sediment-bed temperature series to establish relationships with sediment depth (Figure 8, a and b).

Figure 8. Relationships between sediment height and amplitude ratio (left), and phase differences (right). Solid lines and shaded areas indicate mean \pm standard deviation values resulted from the analysis of two dry weather temperature time series, respectively. Source: Regueiro-Picallo et al. (2023a).

This same procedure can be applied to the study of sediment accumulation in other UDS. The following sections describe the application of this methodology to estimate the depth of sediment in gully pots. In contrast to sewer pipes in which we considered a frequency domain analysis, the heat transfer processes in gully pots are studied in the time domain. In these systems, the temperature exchange introduced by the runoff water during rainfall events is analyzed. The temperature exchange is diffused through the sediment layer, establishing relationships to estimate the depth. For this purpose, several laboratory and field campaigns were carried out.

3.2. Application of heat transfer process analysis for estimating sediment depths in gully pots

Gully pots are transition infrastructures between the surface runoff flows and the pipeline drainage network, acting as small sediment traps. They collect solid particles that settle from surface runoff and wash-off (Rietveld et al., 2020), which results in decreasing the sediment loads during rainfall events and, subsequently, preventing the overloading of the downstream treatment systems.

There are thousands of gully pots in any urban area and, therefore, they need a cleaning system to prevent sediments from causing blockages that lead to flooding of the system. The cleaning strategies are carried out, in the best case, periodically or punctually, in case a blockage problem is detected. Therefore, a monitoring system

would facilitate the cleaning operations and, subsequently, optimize the costs of this service. Three experimental campaigns were performed to apply the system based on temperature measurements in gully pots:

- First campaign: measuring the thermal patterns in real gully pots to design a laboratory experimental campaign that could reproduce these conditions.
- Second campaign: understanding the heat transfer processes in gully pots as a function of different variables: sediment type and depths, hydrodynamics (flow rates), and temperature gradients.
- Third campaign: application of the monitoring system in a field campaign.

Data from these campaigns are available in Regueiro-Picallo et al. (2023b).

3.2.1. Temperatures in gully pots

The first campaign consisted of temperature measurements of two gully pots. The objective of the campaign was to know the dynamics of the runoff water temperature entering a gully pot. For this purpose, the temperature of the water layer ponded in the gully pot was measured during several rainfall events. Each setup consisted of a battery-powered Arduino MKR Zero microcontroller, which recorded temperatures from DS18B20 sensors on a microSD card. The two monitoring setups were installed at the DELTARES campus (Delft, The Netherlands) (Figure 9a). In addition to the temperature data, rainfall data were collected from a weather station installed on the same campus (Figure 9b).

Figure 9. Battery-powered system for measuring temperature dynamics in real gully pots (left), and weather station at Deltares Campus (right) (MetOffice, 2023). Source: Regueiro-Picallo et al. (2023b).

Most of the rains showed that the temperature of the inflow was lower than the ponded water, i.e., the water in gully pots cools down, resulting in negative temperature gradients. In addition, the temperature exchange introduced by the rainfall was fast (ca. 15 min.), which accelerates the temperature mixing processes in the water layer of the gully pot (water convection). Figure 10 shows the temperature variation in the water layer of a gully pot during consecutive rainfall events. The observed dynamics were used to design the experimental campaign in a full-scale gully pot setup.

Figure 10. Temperature time series in the water layer of a gully pot at Deltares campus and rainfall intensity data under wet weather conditions. Data source: Regueiro-Picallo et al. (2023b).

3.2.2. Laboratory experimental campaign

The experimental setup consisted of a 1:1 scaled model gully pot located in the Hydro Hall facilities at Deltares (Delft, The Netherlands). The gully pot model was made of PMMA and the dimensions were $35 \times 35 \times 101 \text{ cm}^3$. In addition, it had a grated lateral inflow, and a flow outlet opening located 39 cm from the bottom. Further details of the geometry can be found in Rietveld (2021).

The gully pot was placed inside a temperature control tank of dimensions $45 \times 84 \times 95 \text{ cm}^3$. The outer tank was filled with deionised water and included a temperature control system via a NESLAB RTE-211 water bath (ThermFisher Scientific, The Netherlands). In addition, a system of PVC pipes and connectors led the outflow to a water tank of 550 L which acted as a reservoir and included (i) a deflector to force the sedimentation of particles resuspended from the gully pot, (ii) a second temperature control system with a NESLAB ThermoFlex2500 (ThermFisher Scientific, The Netherlands), and (iii) a hydraulic pump with a discharge capacity of 4500 L/h. The setup was operated in a closed loop by pumping the water from the 550 L water tank to the gully pot inlet. Figure 11 summarizes the experimental setup.

Figure 11. Photo (left) and scheme (right) of the experimental setup. Source: Regueiro-Picallo et al. (2023b).

24 DS18B20 sensors were installed to measure the temperatures in the experimental setup: i) water reservoir, ii) temperature control tank, iii) inflow, iv) gully pot, and v) room temperature. Inside the gully pot, 5 sensors were placed at the bottom and 2 sensors on the walls every 5 cm from the bottom up to 30 cm. In addition, a Proportional-Integral (PI) control system was developed to establish and control the inflow. The system consisted of a Magnetic Inductive Flowmeter DMH (KOBOLD, USA) and a solenoid valve (Air Torque, Italy). Besides, a SIPART PS2 positioner (SIEMENS, France) with air supply was required to control the opening and closing system of the solenoid valve. These devices were installed in the rigid PVC pipe (DN 32mm) before the gully pot inlet.

The lab-scale experiments replicated the temperature variations in gully pots, which occur because of the mixing of runoff water, pounded water, and sediment bed deposits. Temperature gradients were introduced by setting different temperature setpoints in the control systems, i.e., deionized and 550L water tanks. The tests started by pumping the water to the gully pot inlet once the temperature gradient was stabilised. The PI control system was used to establish and control the inflow (hydrographs, Figure 12a). The inflow was homogeneously mixed with the pounded water layer in the gully pot without causing significant erosion of the sediment-bed layer. A heat diffusion process was thus initiated through the sediment layer. Once the established hydrograph was completed, the heat recovery phase of the system kept on being measured (Figure 12b).

Figure 12. Inflow hydrographs (left) and example of temperature measurements in the gully pot (right). Source: Regueiro-Picallo et al. (2023b).

A total of 56 tests were carried out because of the combination of the following parameters:

- 5 sediment levels: 5, 10, 15, 20, and 25 cm.
- 3 sediment samples: inorganic (sand), organic (gully pot sediments), mix (50% sand and 50% gully pot sediments). Washed sand with a grain size distribution between 0.4 – 0.8 mm was used as inorganic sediments. Furthermore, two gully pot samples were collected from different locations: Deltares (Delft – The Netherlands), and Neeselände (Rotterdam – The Netherlands). These samples were used for the organic tests. Table 1 summarizes the thermal properties of the samples, which were measured with a TP01 sensor (Hukseflux, The Netherlands).
- 3 hydrographs with a peak flow rate of 0.4 L/s at 5 min, 10 min, and 15 min (Hydro 1, 2 and 3 in Figure 12a). Only the Hydro 2 conditions were tested for organic and mixed sediment compounds.
- 2 temperature gradients: -5.5°C and -3.0°C. The temperature gradient was obtained as the difference between the water temperature in the 550 L tank and the ponded water inside the gully pot before testing.

6 additional tests were performed for inorganic sediments under positive gradient conditions: 3.0°C and 5.5°C.

Table 2. Thermal properties of the sediment samples. Data source: Regueiro-Picallo et al. (2023b).

Sample type	Thermal conductivity (W/m/°C)	Volumetric heat capacity (MJ/m ³ /°C)
Sand	2.168	3.029
Organic (Gully pot)	1.739	2.868
Mix (50/50)	0.808	3.277

A 2D numerical diffusion heat transfer model was used to estimate the sediment depth based on the temperatures at the bottom and walls. The sediment depth estimation was performed by calculating the value that provided the best fit between the experimental and simulated temperature series in the sediment layer (example, Figure 13a). Sediment depths obtained with the temperature-based system were compared with those recorded with measuring tapes (Figure 13b). The maximum errors observed were less than 3 cm and the mean absolute errors (MAE) were estimated at 0.6 cm.

Figure 13. Experimental and simulated temperatures in the water and sediment layer: bottom and wall at a height of 5 cm (left), and comparison between sediment depth estimations performed with the temperature-based systems and measurements performed with a measuring tape (right). Data source: Regueiro-Picallo et al. (2023b).

3.2.3. Field experimental campaign

Devices for **MON**itoring Temperatures in **SE**diments (MONTSE) were developed for field gully pot measurements. Field devices were a simplified version of the system used for laboratory testing. Each device consisted of an IP67 insulated box that contained a data collection system for four temperature sensors and was powered by a battery (3.6 V, 5200 mAh). The boxes were designed to be attached to the underside of the iron gully pot covers by using magnets. As a result, they were not visible to minimise vandalism issues.

MONTSE devices included sensors to measure the temperature of the pounded water layer, the air, and the sediment-bed at the bottom and at 10 cm from the bottom of the gully pots. In some devices, the air temperature sensor was replaced by one for measuring the soil temperature. In addition, the sensor deployment in the gully pots was improved by using DN 12 mm PVC pipes to rigidize the set up and facilitate the installation in the field. Two sensor orientations were used (Figure 14a). The horizontal sensor orientation was similar to laboratory setup by placing the temperature sensors at the bottom and attached to the walls of the gully pots. The vertical orientation was developed for practical reasons because the gully pot cleaning companies use powerful vacuum

cleaners with circular heads that would destroy a horizontal-oriented device, but do not reach the corners of the scupper. Therefore, vertical-oriented devices would safely operate at the gully pot corners.

An updated version of MONTSE was developed including the measurement of the sediment thermal properties. For this purpose, this version integrated a Dual-Probe Heat-Pulse (DPHP) system. This system was built by placing a heater cartridge close to the temperature sensor at the bottom of the gully pot, similar to Ravazzani (2017). By measuring the heat-pulse introduced in the sediment layer and the subsequent heat-recovery, the sediment thermal properties can be measured. This heat-pulse system showed a high energy consumption and, therefore, a more powerful battery (12 V, 1.2 A) (Figure 14b).

Figure 14. MONTSE boxes for performing field measurements in gully pots with vertical- and horizontal- oriented configurations (left) and MONTSE box including a DPHP system to determine the thermal properties of the sediment (right). Source: Regueiro-Picallo et al. (2023b).

Six MONTSE devices were installed at three locations (two per location) in South Holland (The Netherlands):

- ABC Westland (The Hague, The Netherlands).
- Deltares campus (Delft, The Netherlands).
- Neeselände (Rotterdam, The Netherlands).

As a result of the field campaigns, temperature time series were collected for several months. To estimate the sediment build-up in gully pots, temperature gradients caused by rainfall events were first identified in the time series. For this purpose, we only focused on the rainfall events causing a negative gradient and we established a threshold to detect rainfall events in the water temperature time series of -1°C in time intervals of 30 min. This means that we considered a rain event with significant influence on heat transfer processes to have occurred when the temperature in the water layer dropped by 1°C compared to the temperature 30 minutes earlier. Thus, rainfall events within the temperature time series could be detected and selected to perform the sediment depth estimation.

Once an event was selected, the same procedure was followed as in the experimental laboratory campaign. The sediment depth estimation was performed by calculating the value that provided the best fit between the field measurements in the sediment layer and simulated temperature series using the 2D numerical diffusion heat transfer model. Figure 15a shows the comparison between the field measurements of a sensor installed at a height of 10 cm from the bottom inside a gully pot at Deltares campus and the simulated temperature time series that provided the best-fit sediment depth. To obtain the best fit of the sediment depth in each event, the temperature

in the water layer, the thermal properties of the sediments, and the convective heat transfer coefficient between the sediment layer and the gully pot contours were introduced as input variables to the 2D model. The thermal properties of the sediments were measured from samples except in the system that included the heat-pulse method (Figure 10b). The convective heat transfer coefficient was estimated from the thermal conductivity of the gully pot material (concrete: $1 \text{ W/m}^2\text{/}^\circ\text{C}$) and its thickness (5 cm), resulting in a value of $20 \text{ W/m}^2\text{/}^\circ\text{C}$.

By analyzing each of the rainfall events independently, it was possible to estimate the sediment build-up process in the gully pots. Sediment depths obtained with the temperature-based system were compared with stick measurements. For this purpose, we used the same stick developed by Rietveld et al. (2020) to measure the sediment depths in gully pots. Figure 15b shows the comparison between both methods of the sediment build-up process in a gully pot at Deltares campus. The sediment depth absolute errors were less than 3 cm, similar to that reported in the laboratory tests.

Figure 15. Field measurements and simulated temperatures that provided the best-fit sediment depth considering a rainfall event (left) and comparison of the build-up process in a gully pot at Deltares campus based on stick measurements and estimations from the temperature-based system (right). Data source: Regueiro-Picallo et al. (2023b) and MetOffice (2023).

3.3. Concluding remarks

The MONTSE system and the analysis of heat transfer processes showed satisfactory results in the estimation of sediment depths in urban drainage systems. This report presents the fundamentals of this methodology, as well as an example of application in gully pots. Although this methodology showed a high accuracy under laboratory conditions, several constraints must be considered when field measurements are performed. First, rainfall events are required so that the runoff water entering the gully pot causes a sufficient heat exchange to estimate the sediment depth. Second, rainfall events that cause negative gradients are preferable because positive temperature gradients lead to stratification processes in the water layer. As a result of the measurement campaign, we established that the heat exchange is sufficient to estimate the sediment thickness when the temperature gradient in the water layer was -1°C or less by comparing temperatures in a 30 min window.

To improve the accuracy of sediment depth estimations, heat pulses are recommended to be included within the MONTSE system. The heat pulses can determine the thermal properties of the sediments, which are crucial variable to estimate the sediment depth. In addition, collecting sediment samples from gully pots and determining their thermal properties in the laboratory is an alternative to reduce the cost and energy consumption of the MONTSE system.

Surrogate methods can also be developed to integrate sediment depth estimation models into the MONTSE system microcontroller (edge computing). Surrogate models simplify the solution of differential equations such as the

diffusion heat transfer equation. Consequently, computational cost of sediment depth estimation could be reduced. Also, the volume of transferred data could be reduced by avoiding transferring the temperature time series. Furthermore, data transfer volume would be reduced by avoiding transferring the temperature time series.

All these improvements would result in the development of systems for monitoring sediment accumulation in urban drainage systems. From the maintenance point of view of these systems, the optimal time for cleaning could be determined to avoid the loss of hydraulic efficiency and, subsequently, the risk of flooding and polluting overflows in urban areas. For this application, the MONTSE system could be optimized by reducing the number of sensors per unit. Using the differences between a pair of temperature sensors would be sufficient to determine the critical sediment depth at which cleanup should be performed. From the point of view of sediment transport research in urban drainage systems, monitoring sediment build-up processes would lead to the development of accurate transport models to predict pollutant loads during dry and wet weather periods.

4. Definition of standard methods to assess permeable pavement performance and increase understanding of the clogging process.

Permeable pavements have emerged as a solution to address stormwater management challenges in urban catchments. Permeable pavements allow rainwater to infiltrate into the ground, reducing runoff and helping to recharge groundwater aquifers. These pavements also play a crucial role in mitigating the peak runoff during heavy rainfall events into stormwater drainage systems. This avoids, in both cases, overwhelming urban drainage systems and contributing to mitigation of water pollution. However, the long-term performance of permeable pavements can be affected by clogging problems caused by different kind of sediments accumulated in urban catchments during dry weather (Nolting, B.; Schönberger O.; Harting, K., 2005). Permeable pavements maintenance is thus one important point that must be considered in the design and installation of the pavement. Several factors influence the permeability of these pavements, such as age, wetting of the pavement or contamination levels. Understanding these factors is thus crucial for maintaining and optimising the long-term performance of permeable pavements in different urban contexts.

This section presents a series of laboratory tests that were conducted to develop and assess new and existing methods for analysing pavement performance and to gain insights into how these systems operate during their lifetime. The test method and specification used are based on the standards set by the Deutsches Institut für Bautechnik (DIBt), the German Institute for Construction Engineering. They are focused on determining hydraulic permeability and material retention of a cobblestone pavement with permeable joints under different sources of contamination, such as plastic dust and particulate sediments with different granulometrics. The work is part of a new joint research line between IKT and UDC towards the development of standardised methods to assess the long-term behaviour of different permeable pavement types during their lifetime. This will allow for improved design and maintenance to optimise the long-term performance of pavements.

4.1. Test setup description

4.1.1. Characteristics of the IKT irrigation system (rainfall simulator)

The IKT irrigation system (rainfall simulator) is used for tests for the DIBt approval of permeable pavements.¹ In addition, the test rig can be used for scientific research on infiltration, runoff behaviour and pollutant retention of permeable pavements.

The pavement to be tested is installed in a frame of 1 m². The facility consists of a stainless-steel test pan (Figure 16), an irrigation system and devices for measuring flow, quantity and quality of infiltrated water and surface water run-off.

Figure 16. Components of the IKT irrigation system for testing water-permeable pavements.

¹ DIBt: Deutsches Institut für Bautechnik (German Institute for Construction Engineering).

Figure 17. Photo of the experimental facility.

The IKT irrigation system consists of three parts (figure 17), a rainfall generator system (A) placed above the frame, a flexible exchangeable/interchangeable frame (B) in which the pavements are installed, and a base with a collecting funnel (C) for the water.

The interchangeable frame (B), in which the pavement installed, is closed off from below by a fine sieve made of stainless steel (figure 18, a). The seepage water that has passed through a pavement can exit through this sieve. The side walls of the standard frame have a height of 12 cm, allowing for 4 cm bedding and 8 cm paving stone. Transport lugs are attached to the outside of the reinforced frame so that the frame, including its contents, can be transported and installed in the rig with the help of a crane. This is necessary because the products to be tested are usually installed in the frame outside the test stand. Thus, in the case of several test frames, pavements can be installed and removed simultaneously while others are being tested. There is a drainage channel at the outer edge of the frame to collect the surface water run-off from across the pavement. The water running off to the side is collected via an outlet and weighed in a container placed on a scale. The weight-time relationship can be used to determine the flow rate. The infiltrated water that leaves the rig through the fine sieve is collected in a geometrically accurately measured trough with a pressure sensor. The flow rate can be determined via the volumetric level-time relationship.

Figure 18. Interchangeable frame (a) and irrigation system (b).

The rainfall simulator system (A) is above the interchangeable frame. It consists of an acrylic tray, in which stainless steel cannulas are embedded at the bottom (figure 18, b). The tray is a part of an acrylic tank. The cannulas are located at 4 cm from each other. A total of 625 cannulas enables realistic irrigation of the surface. The cannulas are Sterican® cannulas from the company B. Braun SE with an inner diameter of 0.9 mm, which can be obtained from medical retailers.

The principle of the inlet section can be described as follows. The water for this sprinkler system is fed into the irrigation system from a supply tank via a centrifugal pump and then drips onto the pavement via the cannulas. The rainfall intensity is measured via a Coriolis mass flow meter in the inlet and controlled via the pump. A coarse filter is in the inlet of the system to remove particles from the water that could clog the cannulas.

The rainfall intensity is controlled by the water pressure. To release the excess air in the acrylic tank, a valve is opened on the top of the sprinkler during filling. When water comes out of the valve, it is closed and the rainfall starts at the desired intensity.

Figure 19 shows the installation layout of paving stones for the tests.

Figure 19: Installation scheme of the paving stones (a) (resource: DIBt) and installed paving stones in the interchangeable frame of the IKT irrigation system (b).

4.1.2. Test criteria and characteristics of the material to be tested

The following test criteria were chosen for the experiments:

I. irrigation

The IKT irrigation system (rainfall simulator) can be used to simulate rainfall up to 1,200 l/(s*ha). Rainfall between 200 and 540 l/(s*ha) were of interest for the investigation in this project, based on DIBt approval principles and FGSV.

II: pavement

A wastewater-treating surface pavement called geoSTON, from Klostermann GmbH & Co. KG, of Coesfeld, Germany, was used for these tests. This product has dimensions of 20/10/8 cm and has a DIBt type approval (Z-84.1-2). According to the manufacturer, the paving stone is made of porous (lightweight aggregate) concrete.

The average joint spacing is 5 mm. This corresponds to a joint proportion of approx. 5.9 %. The joint material consists of basalt chippings with the following properties according to TL Gestein-StB 04: grain group 1/3.

III: bedding material

The bedding material consists of limestone chippings with the following properties according to TL Gestein-StB 04: grain size group 2/5.

IV: Sediments

Following sediments were used for the tests to cause clogging:

- Millisil dust (MD)

This sediment is a standardized Millisil W4 iron-free grinding of processed silica sand typically used in industry and it is used as sediment for the German DIBt approval test. The particle size distribution has a maximum diameter of 250 μm with mean diameter of 64 μm . The density is 2,650 kg/m^3 .

- Street dust (SD)

This sediment was obtained from road dust from parking lots in the UDC campus. The sediment was calcined at 550 °C and classified into sediment fractions to compound a realistic graded road deposit sediment with a d50 of 282 μm . The maximum size was sieved to 1 mm. The density is 2,929 kg/m^3 .

- Tyre dust (TD)

Description The particle size distribution has a maximum diameter of 200 μm with mean diameter of 64 μm . The density is 1,160 kg/m^3 . The material is used for is used as a filler and extender in the concrete industry.

Figure 20 shows the particle size distribution of these three sediments used to analyse the clogging, measured using a laser coulter counter (Beckam-Coulter LS 13 320).

Figure 20. Particle size distribution of the three sediments used for clogging tests.

4.2. Experimental procedure

The pavement installation (see above, chapter 4.1) was used for testing the behaviour of different kinds of sediments regarding clogging. Basically, the question investigated was to what extent the various sediments differ in terms of their clogging behaviour in water-permeable pavements. This is particularly important with regard to creating standardised test procedures for permeable pavement with boundary conditions that are as close as possible to reality.

IKT and UDC developed a test procedure for these three sediments which takes up the requirements of the DIBt and goes beyond them. In the requirements, the DIBt only takes into account pollution accumulation over 10 years. The IKT/UDC-test programme picks up on the fact that permeable pavements are in operation for much longer than 10 years. Therefore, this test procedure relates to a service life of 40 years

For comparative purposes, the same experimental setup of pavement and bedding was used for each sediment. The test procedure consisted of the following:

- Test run 1 (according to DIBt):

At first the initial permeability was checked for each sediment according to DIBt test standard (requirements: rainfall of 540 l/s*ha => 200 mm/h). The rain duration was set at 30 min to achieve uniform moisture penetration (pre-saturation) of the stone. After this, a rain simulation with a duration of 5 minutes with the same rainfall was made to check the infiltration.

- Test run 2 (according to DIBt):

In test run 2 clogging time for one of the materials was checked. A pollution loading for 10 years was added at the beginning of the test run on the surface (add 500 g/m²). Then rainfall with a duration of 180 minutes and a rate of 72 mm/h (200 l/s*ha) was applied.

- Test run 3 (according to DIBt):

In test run 3 the permeability after clogging was checked again. According to the requirements a rainfall rate of 100 mm/h has to be applied for 30 minutes followed by a test phase of 5 minutes for testing performance.

- Test runs 4 – 10 (according to IKT/UDC test procedure):

In test runs 4-10 the same test run as in step 1-3 was repeated three times for the addition of 40 years of pollution on the pavement. Test run 5 was a longer break, to simulate a longer dry period.

Table 3 to 5 shows the test procedure for Millisil (MD), Street dust (SD) and tyre dust (TD).

Table 3. Test runs, duration and breaks for Millisil (MD).

No. of test run with Millisil (MD) / procedure	Rain duration [min]	Break after test [h:mm]
1 (DIBt)	35	0:07
2 (DIBt) – adding pollution (500 g/m ²)	180	0:11
3 (DIBt)	35	0:07
4 (IKT/UDC) – adding pollution (500 g/m ²)	180	16:25
5 (IKT/UDC)	-	-
6 (IKT/UDC)	35	0:15
7 (IKT/UDC) – adding pollution (500 g/m ²)	180	0:10
8 (IKT/UDC)	35	0:10
9 (IKT/UDC) – adding pollution (500 g/m ²)	180	0:07
10 (IKT/UDC)	35	-

Table 4. Test runs, duration and breaks for street dust (SD).

No. of test run with Street dust (SD) / procedure	Rain duration [min]	Break after test [h:mm]
1 (DIBt)	35	0:15
2 (DIBt) – adding pollution (500 g/m ²)	180	0:06
3 (DIBt)	35	0:09
4 (IKT/UDC) – adding pollution (500 g/m ²)	180	15:52
5 (IKT/UDC)	-	-
6 (IKT/UDC)	35	0:08
7 (IKT/UDC) – adding pollution (500 g/m ²)	180	0:10
8 (IKT/UDC)	35	0:10
9 (IKT/UDC) – adding pollution (500 g/m ²)	180	0:11
10 (IKT/UDC)	35	-

Table 5. Test runs, duration and breaks for tyre dust (TD).

No. of test run with tyre dust (TD) / procedure	Rain duration [min]	Break after test [h:mm]
1 (DIBt)	35	0:12
2 (DIBt) – adding pollution (500 g/m ²)	180	0:12
3 (DIBt)	35	0:13
4 (IKT/UDC) – adding pollution (500 g/m ²)	180	15:41

5 (IKT/UDC)	-	-
6 (IKT/UDC)	35	0:34
7 (IKT/UDC) – adding pollution (500 g/m ²)	180	0:09
8 (IKT/UDC)	35	0:11
9 (IKT/UDC) – adding pollution (500 g/m ²)	180	0:09
10 (IKT/UDC)	35	-

4.3. Results

The findings are summarised in figure 21, which shows the infiltration rate and run off volume from street dust and the Millisil dust are similar. Both materials are inorganic and have a density of 2,650 and 2,929 kg/m³. These values are different for the tyre dust. One possible reason could be the lower density of tyre dust, half of the other two materials. Moreover, the tyre dust is building agglomerate, so it is larger and does not infiltrate into the joints between the stones as easily as the other two materials.

The measurements of water volumes have an error of 5.9% +- 4.8% over all measurements.

Figure 21. Infiltration rate (INF) and run off volume (RUN) of the three test materials: street dust (SD), Millisil dust (MD) and tyre dust (TD).

Figures 22, 23 and 24 shows the pavements after all tests conducted with a pollution loading of 40 years. The distribution of Millisil dust (MD) and street dust (SD) is very similar. This is corresponding to the density, which is also very similar. The tyre dust (TD) is located much more on the surface and not so much infiltrated. This is corresponding to its behaviour, that the material is a building agglomerate and has a smaller density and larger particle size.

Figure 22. Change frame with pavement after simulation a pollution of 40 years with Millisil (MD).

Figure 23. Change frame with pavement after simulation a pollution of 40 years with street dust (SD).

Figure 24. Change frame with pavement after simulation a pollution of 40 years with tyre dust (TD).

Next to the water balance the focus was on the behaviour of the test materials in passing through the test setup into the infiltrated water. The quantity of each material used was 2,000.00 g. The particles that were collected from the infiltration water were 43.00 g (MD), 1.47g (SD) and 16,77 g (TD).

The quantities of material that washed off the surface and became lodged in the gaps between stones and in the bedding material underneath were not specifically measured for this experiment. Visual observations suggest that the tyre dust was more easily transported across the surface in runoff, whilst the other two materials more easily penetrated into the joints between the stones.

The main conclusions of this tests can be described as follows (for a simulation time of 40 years):

- Millisil and street dust showed similar behaviour. Supplementary tests with tyre dust (lighter and larger than both mineral materials) showed a different behaviour. More tyre dust material was retained on the surface and less infiltration of this material into the joints was observed.
- The real pollution processes on the road are not only mineral based. They are influenced by a mixture of organic and mineral substances with different densities. The mixed compound (street-dust – SD) used in the project is closer to reality, but it was extracted and processed with great effort. Moreover, it is difficult to get reproducibility (quality, composition) of this material. In contrast, Millisil is always available in a similar quality, because it is an industrially manufactured product, but it is not so close to reality. There is, consequently, a need for further research on test materials to ensure representativeness and reproducibility.
- Infiltration generally decreased for Street dust (SD), Millisil (MD) and Tyre dust (TD) as a longer period of pollution (10 to 40 years) was simulated, as expected, indicating the need for ongoing maintenance of such systems to maintain their performance.

5. Conclusions and contribution towards the objectives of Co-UDlabs

The study “**Measuring the interception of microplastics by stilling stormwater basins**” (Chapter 2) focused on PVC and PET particles with sizes ranging from 80µm to 500µm and densities of 1.36 and 1.38 respectively. To address the scientific questions, the study was divided into two parts. The first part looked at the settling velocity of MPs using the VICAS protocol. Results showed that the settling velocity of investigated MPs had the same order of magnitude as that of suspended solids. The results of the study also show that the higher the MPs concentration, the faster the particles settle.

The interception rate of MPs through the DSM-flux was also assessed. The results showed that the interception rate is 25% particularly for PVC MPs at a flow rate of 5 L/s. INSA is involved in a national program in France on MPs sources, transport, and fate in urban drainage to which this study relates.

In the study “**Measuring sediment deposits in urban drainage infrastructure from high-resolution temperature signals**” (chapter 3) the devices for Monitoring Temperatures in Sediments (MONTSE system) and the analysis of heat transfer processes showed satisfactory results in the estimation of sediment depths in urban drainage systems. This report presents the fundamentals of this methodology, as well as an example of application in gully pots. Although this methodology showed a high accuracy under laboratory conditions, several constraints must be considered when field measurements are performed. First, rainfall events are required so that the runoff water entering the gully pot causes a sufficient heat exchange to estimate the sediment depth. Second, rainfall events that cause negative gradients are preferable because positive temperature gradients lead to stratification processes in the water layer. As a result of the measurement campaign, we established that the heat exchange is sufficient to estimate the sediment thickness when the temperature gradient in the water layer was -1°C or less by comparing temperatures in a 30 min window.

To improve the accuracy of sediment depth estimations, heat pulses are recommended to be included within the MONTSE system. The heat pulses can determine the thermal properties of the sediments, which are crucial variable to estimate the sediment depth. In addition, collecting sediment samples from gully pots and determining their thermal properties in the laboratory is an alternative to reduce the cost and energy consumption of the MONTSE system.

Surrogate methods can also be developed to integrate sediment depth estimation models into the MONTSE system microcontroller (edge computing). Surrogate models simplify the solution of differential equations such as the diffusion heat transfer equation. Consequently, computational cost of sediment depth estimation could be reduced. Also, the volume of transferred data could be reduced by avoiding transferring the temperature time series. Furthermore, data transfer volume would be reduced by avoiding transferring the temperature time series.

All these improvements would result in the development of systems for monitoring sediment accumulation in urban drainage systems. From the maintenance point of view of these systems, the optimal time for cleaning could be determined to avoid the loss of hydraulic efficiency and, subsequently, the risk of flooding and polluting overflows in urban areas. For this application, the MONTSE system could be optimized by reducing the number of sensors per unit. Using the differences between a pair of temperature sensors would be sufficient to determine the critical sediment depth at which cleanup should be performed. From the point of view of sediment transport research in urban drainage systems, monitoring sediment build-up processes would lead to the development of accurate transport models to predict pollutant loads during dry and wet weather periods.

In the study “**Definition of standard methods to assess permeable pavement performance and increase understanding of clogging process**” (chapter 4), a test procedure was developed (IKT/UDC-test programme), which simulated a lifetime of 40 years. The current test programme of the Deutsches Institut für Bautechnik (DIBt) only simulates a period of 10 years. With the IKT/UDC-test programme, tests were carried out using various test media designed to simulate road pollution (Millisil, collected street dust and tyre dust). In this context, insights were gained into the clogging process of permeable pavements and there was further development of a procedure for testing their performance using “road pollution” test mediums.

The real pollution processes on the road are not only mineral based. They are influenced by a mixture of organic and mineral substances with different densities. The street dust compound used in the study was made from in-situ samples collected in the field and was closer to reality than Millisil (MD), which is usually used for approval tests of DIBt in Germany. However, extracting and processing street dust requires great effort, and its practice would be very difficult to reproduce (quality, composition) for comparative testing purposes. In contrast Millisil (MD) is always available in a similar quality, because it is an industrially manufactured product, but it is not so close to reality. There is a need for further research on identifying a suitable, reproducible test media.

Millisil (MD) and street dust (SD) showed similar results regarding behaviour. Supplementary tests with tyre dust (TD) (lighter than both mineral materials) showed a different behaviour. In this case more material was retained on the surface and less infiltration of this material into the joints was obtained.

Infiltration generally decreased for Street dust (SD), Millisil (MD) and Tyre dust (TD) over the pollution period, as expected, indicating the need for maintenance.

6. References

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